

Kinetics and mechanism of iridium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of ethylene glycol and methyl glycol by hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium

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The iridium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of ethylene glycol and methyl glycol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ion is first order at lower concentration of organic substrate and hexacyanoferrate(III) ion, tending towards zero order at their higher concentrations. The order of reaction with respect to hydroxide ion and iridium(III) chloride is unity even upto many folds of variation. The course of reaction has been considered to proceed through the formation of an activated complex between the anion of organic substrate and iridium(III) species. This complex slowly reacts with hexacyanoferrate(III) ion resulting into Ir^I species and the corresponding intermediate product. The fast oxidation of Ir^I with hexacyanoferrate(III) results Ir^{III} species and hexacyanoferrate(II).

Platinum metals¹ are used as catalyst in the oxidation of organic compounds by ferricyanide ion in aqueous alkaline medium. An effective catalyst for the oxidation of organic compounds in alkaline medium is iridium(III) chloride². In the present study an attempt has been made to study the oxidation of ethylene glycol and methyl glycol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium by using iridium(III) chloride as catalyst.

Results and Discussion

The iridium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of ethylene glycol (EG) and methyl glycol (MG) has been studied in aqueous alkaline medium using condition where the uncatalyzed reaction becomes negligible. The results reveal that the kinetic behavior of both EG and MG are the same. The oxidation of EG and MG follows nearly first order kinetics at lower concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III) ions and organic substrate (Figs. 1 and 2). The concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) and organic substrate were varied from 1.0×10^{-3} to 10.0×10^{-3} M and 1.0×10^{-2} to 10.0×10^{-2} M, respectively. The initial rates were calculated by plotting remaining hexacyanoferrate(III) ion vs time. The straight line plots confirm the first order kinetics with respect to hydroxide ion concentration. The hydroxide ion concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-1} to 9.0×10^{-1} M for MG and EG. The effect of variation of iridium(III)

chloride shows first order kinetics even upto its many fold variation for both the organic substrates. A plot of log rate vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ has been found to be straight line with positive slope suggesting thereby the involvement of two similarly charged reacting species in the reaction for both the glycols.

Fig. 1. Effect of $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ on the reaction rate : (A) [ethylene glycol] = 8.0×10^{-2} M, $[NaOH] = 0.3$ M, $[IrCl_3] = 5.66 \times 10^{-5}$ M, $\mu = 1.00$ M and 35° , (B) [methyl glycol] = 7.0×10^{-2} M, $[NaOH] = 0.5$ M, $[IrCl_3] = 5.66 \times 10^{-5}$ M, $\mu = 1.00$ M at 35° .

Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking hexacyanoferrate(III) in large excess as compared to the organic substrate in different ratios and the observations were made for a long period. The experimental results reveal that for the oxidation of one molecule of EG and MG, 8 and 4 molecules of hexacyanoferrate(III) are consumed, respectively. The stoichiometry of the reaction might be represented as

where R = $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{CH}_3$, for EG and MG, respectively.

Fig. 2. Effect of [substrate] on the reaction rate at 35° : (A) ethylene glycol : $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.6 \text{ M}$, $[\text{IrCl}_3] = 5.66 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 1.00 \text{ M}$, (B) methyl glycol : $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{IrCl}_3] = 5.66 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 1 \text{ M}$.

Now on the basis of the experimental results it is worth to assume the first order dependence of the reaction rate on lower concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III) and organic substrate. Similarly, reaction rate shows first order dependence on hydroxide and catalyst. Thus under these conditions a probable rate law might be given for EG and MG as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = k[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] [\text{Organic substrate}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] \quad (1)$$

where [Fey] is the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion and k is a constant. The values of k could not be calculated due to non-availability of the proper conditions.

Before proposing the probable oxidation scheme, it is interesting to know the probable species of iridium(III) chloride in alkaline medium. The iridium trichloride in hydrochloric acid medium has been reported³ to exist in the form of IrCl_6^{3-} species. It is also reported that Ir^{III} and Ir^{I}

ions are the stable species^{3,4} of iridium and there is no evidence of the formation of Ir^{II} species in literature. Further, the aquation⁵ of IrCl_6^{3-} gives $[\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$, $[\text{IrCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^-$ and $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ species.

Since no retarding effect of chloride ion was observed hence hydrated species can not be the reactive species. Thus $(\text{IrCl}_6)^{3-}$ has been considered as the only reacting species of IrCl_3 in alkaline medium.

Thus, on the basis of the above evidences, the oxidation scheme of aforesaid glycols might be described as

(S)

(C)

+ Intermediate product + H^+ (III)

where R = CH_2OH for ethylene glycol and CH_3OCH_2 for methyl glycol and S represents organic substrate. The anion of the organic substrate⁶ combines with IrCl_6^{3-} to form a loosely bonded complex-C which decomposes slowly with one molecule of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ ion to iridium(I) chloride and intermediate product. The intermediate product gets oxidized to an acid through a fast step due to which it is not possible to detect the intermediate product. Iridium(I) chloride quickly gets oxidized to iridium(III) chloride by two molecules of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion via one-electron transfer process.

From the above mechanism the concentration of complex formed and Ir^{III} would be

$$\frac{d[\text{complex}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{S}^-] [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] - k_{-1} [\text{Complex}] - k_2 [\text{Complex}] [\text{Fey}] \quad (2)$$

$$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] + [\text{Complex}] \quad (3)$$

The rate of disappearance of ferricyanide can be given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Complex}] [\text{Fey}] \quad (4)$$

At steady state and with the help of eqns. (2)–(4) the rate of disappearance of ferricyanide is given as

$$R = -\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 K[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{k_{-1} + k_2[\text{Fey}] + k_1 K[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (5)$$

Eqn. (5) has been multiplied by a factor 2 because during the course of reaction Ir^{III} reduces to Ir^{I} . Hence its oxidation requires two molecules of ferricyanide.

On the basis of the experimental results at low concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion and organic substrate, the value of $k_2[\text{Fey}]$ and $k_1 K[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]$ will be quite small and hence eqn. (5) reduces to

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = 2 k_2 K K_1 [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (6)$$

where $K_1 = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}}$

Eqn. (6) clearly accounts the first order kinetics with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III), organic substrate, hydroxide ion and catalyst at very low concentrations.

Eqn. (5) can be verified by rewriting it as

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{1}{2k_2 K K_1 [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{2k_1 K [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{2k_2 [\text{Fey}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}} \quad (7)$$

The plots of $1/\text{rate (R)}$ vs $1/[\text{Fey}]$ and $1/[\text{S}]$ gives straight line with positive intercepts at y-axis. With the help of intercepts of $1/R$ vs $1/[\text{Fey}]^{-1}$ for ethylene glycol and methyl glycol, $k_1 K$ values calculated were 3.3×10^{-1} and 3.1×10^{-1} , respectively. Further, k_2 values were calculated with the help of the intercepts of plots of $1/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ and these values come out to be 2.89 and 1.65 for ethylene glycol and methyl glycol, respectively. These values were calculated at two different concentrations of $[\text{Fey}]$ and $[\text{S}]$. The constancy of $k_1 K$ and k_2 values clearly shows the validity of derived rate law eqn. (5) and the proposed reaction mechanism.

Experimental

Aqueous solutions of ethylene glycol/methyl glycol (AnalaR) were prepared afresh. Solution of iridium trichloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared in very dilute solution of HCl. The final strengths of the HCl and that of iridium trichloride were kept at $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $2.83 \times 10^{-3} M$, respectively. NaOH and potassium ferricyanide (AnalaR) were used. The ionic strength of the system was kept constant by using KCl (E. Merck).

The kinetic experiments were carried out by mixing the required quantity of alcohol solution maintained at a constant temperature with a solution of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, NaOH and iridium(III) chloride kept at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was measured by estimating the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) ion produced after definite time intervals with the standard solution of ceric(IV) sulfate, using ferrion as a redox indicator. The data always gave reproducible results. Paper chromatography and spot test method⁷ confirmed oxalic acid and methyl glycollic acid as the final oxidation products in case of ethylene glycol and methyl glycol, respectively. The solvent used was the solution of butanol, formic acid and water (12 : 2 : 15). Bromophenol blue was used as a locating agent.

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